

Evaluations of Threshold Voltage Stability on COTS SiC DMOSFETs Using Fast Measurements

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Abstract—Threshold voltage (V_T) stability of commercial SiC DMOSFETs during bias-temperature stressing was evaluated using the fast- I_D and fast I_D - V_{GS} measurement techniques at both room and elevated temperatures. Unipolar bias stress results confirmed that there is a rapid recovery of V_T and that all vendors' devices showed the same basic charge-trapping behavior, although some differences were observed in negative bias response at high temperatures. In situ V_T measurements during 10 kHz gate switching showed stable device operation at room temperature but accelerating V_T drift and increasing switching oxide trap densities when operated at 175 °C. V_T hysteresis during high temperature gate switching indicates the presence of a mobile ion or polarization effect in addition to the expected interface- and oxide-trap charging mechanisms.

Index Terms—Power MOSFET, Semiconductor device reliability, Silicon carbide, Stability, Threshold voltage.

I. INTRODUCTION

Threshold voltage degradation has been identified as a key reliability concern facing the widespread adoption of SiC metal-oxide-semiconductor (MOS) technology [1]. This degradation, which appears to be related to the charging and discharging of (near-interfacial) switching oxide traps (SOTs) [2], tends to pull the threshold voltage V_T of SiC MOSFETs towards any applied bias. Additionally, V_T recovers very rapidly following the removal of a stress bias [3]–[5], limiting the usefulness of conventional DC measurement techniques in characterizing this phenomenon. Ultra-fast or “non-recovery” measurement techniques (e.g., [6]), which had been developed to characterize and understand Si negative-bias temperature instability (NBTI), are now being applied to the SiC MOS system [3], [7] and typically record 2–5 \times as much drift as DC measurements. One of the key application spaces for SiC MOS devices is power conditioning [8], [9], but these effects under AC switching are not yet well understood.

For commercial off-the-shelf (COTS) SiC MOS devices, V_T drift at room temperature appears to be fully recoverable [3], but in older SiC MOS the combination of bias and temperature has been found to be enough to activate additional charge traps which manifest as an accelerating drift at longer stress times ($\sim 10^3$ s at 175 °C) [2]. A recent comparison of newer COTS DMOSFETs from two vendors [10] shows a dramatic improvement in stability during both unipolar and bipolar stresses over previous generations for both suppliers. We will report here on new data comparing

these devices using fast threshold measurement methods to evaluate threshold-voltage stability under bias and temperature stressing. Additionally, we will report initial measurements of in situ V_T drift during gate switching to explore the mechanism under more operationally relevant testing conditions.

II. EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

A. Devices Studied

SiC DMOSFETs were purchased from the three main suppliers listed on DigiKey from late 2014 through early 2015 (Cree, Rohm, and ST Microelectronics), who will be referenced below as Vendors A, B, and C. Si MOSFETs from International Rectifier (manufactured circa 1992) were used as a control group for comparison purposes. The specific parts used and their relevant specifications are shown in Table I.

TABLE I. LISTING OF PARTS TESTED AND RELEVANT SPECIFICATIONS

Vendor & Part #	Specifications ^a		
	Max V_{DS} , I_D Rating	Max Gate-Source Voltage	Operating Temperature
Cree C2M0280120D	1200V/10A	-10 V / +25 V	150 °C
Rohm SCT2450KE	1200V/10A	-6 V / +22 V	175 °C
ST Microelectronics SCT20N120	1200V/20A	-10 V / +25 V	200 °C
International Rectifier IRFP250 (Si)	200V/30A	-20 V / +20 V	150 °C

a. Taken from publicly released data sheets

Devices arrived packaged in TO-247s and were soldered into a custom fixture to conduct bias-temperature stress (BTS) tests. Basic parametric measurements were performed at room temperature (and elevated temperature where appropriate) before BTS was applied. Results are presented below on previously-unstressed (as-received) devices.

B. Methods Used

V_T is defined herein as the gate-source bias V_{GS} needed to source a drain current I_D of 1 mA with small drain-source bias V_{DS} applied (~ 100 mV). A Keithley 4200-SCS Parameter Analyzer with 4200-BTI-A Ultra-Fast PMU was used to apply stress biases and record I - V data.

1) Unipolar Stress

For unipolar stresses, we used the fast- I_D method [11] to characterize V_T . A schematic of the V_{GS} test sequence used is

shown in Fig. 1; V_{DS} and the device temperature were held constant. An initial I_D - V_{GS} curve is measured to establish a baseline V_T , which is used to set V_{GS} during the pre-stress and recovery phases. This allows V_T to be measured during pre-stress and recovery without changing V_{GS} . The pre-stress segment is used to stabilize V_T and reduce the influence that any prior biasing may have had on the charge state of the device. A unipolar stress at +15 V (PBTS) or -15 V (NBTS) is then applied, with periodic interruptions to measure V_T as a function of cumulative stress time t_s . In our setup it took approximately 2-5 μ s to switch the gate bias from the stress voltage to the measure voltage, sample I_D , and transition back to the stress. Following the last removal of the stress bias, V_T is measured in recovery as a function of time t_R following the end of the stress. V_T drift is defined as the difference between a V_T measurement and the final, stabilized V_T measured in pre-stress immediately before any application of the stress bias.

Figure 1. Schematic of the gate-source bias V_{GS} during PBTS testing, showing both stressing and measurement portions. NBTS is identical except that during stress $V_{GS} = -15$ V. The temperature and V_{DS} are held constant throughout the sequence.

2) AC Stress

The goal of applying an AC stress is to more closely match a device's typical operating condition than a unipolar (or "DC" bipolar) stress alone can and serve as a more accurate predictor of actual operating reliability. This is particularly true when considering long-term stress testing, since a power device in normal use will rarely if ever experience an extended period at a sustained gate bias. The alternating application of off- and on-state biases limits the exposure length of any individual bias stress but introduces the complication of repeated cycling.

The specific waveform used is shown in Fig. 2. V_T can be measured without interrupting the waveform by sampling I_D during the transitions using appropriate instrumentation. As opposed to the fast- I_D method used for unipolar stress, V_{GS} is varied during measurement and multiple points are taken;

instead of using a static I_D - V_{GS} curve to project V_T , interpolation of the data itself allows determination of V_{GS} at $I_D=1$ mA for a set V_{DS} . For brevity, V_T^+ is the threshold measured during turn-off (following PBS) while V_T^- is measured during turn-on (following NBS). Additionally, the hysteresis between two consecutively measured values is designated as $\Delta V_T (=V_T^+ - V_T^-)$.

Figure 2. Schematic of the V_{GS} waveform during AC stressing. I_D is sampled during the turn-on and -off transitions to measure V_T . During some cycles, V_{DS} is transitioned to 0 V while in the off-state and I_D is measured as normal to correct for capacitive displacement currents.

For the DMOSFETs studied, device capacitance limited the transition time to a few μ s at minimum (compared to typical transitions of ~ 100 ns for a standard gate driver), which places an effective upper limit on switching frequency in order to maintain an appropriate square-wave shape. We chose to use 10 kHz, both because it is a practical limit and because it is in the range of interest for power conditioning.

III. RESULTS

A. Room-Temperature Bias Stressing

Fig. 3 shows the V_T drift during PBS at 25 $^{\circ}$ C observed on a Vendor B device, which was characteristic of devices from all vendors studied. The stress and recovery curves were recorded for a series of increasing cumulative stress times. After each stress, the device was able to fully recover its threshold back to the original value. Subsequent stress curves going to longer t_s produced V_T drifts identical to the earlier results, showing the drift is recoverable and not permanent.

The 25 $^{\circ}$ C PBS results for devices from all vendors are shown in Fig. 4, along with a similarly rated Si MOSFET for comparison. A rapid initial drift is observed in all SiC devices, which quickly settles to a steady linear-with-log-time increase. The recovery occurs as a power law, roughly proportional to

Figure 3. V_T drift during stress (left) and recovery (right) of a typical device during 25 $^{\circ}$ C PBS. Multiple pairs of stress and recovery data were recorded, with increasing total stress time. The stress curves coincide, demonstrating that the device can fully recover between tests under these conditions. The dashed lines connect the end of each stress curve with its corresponding recovery.

$t_R^{-0.15}$ for all cases. Although the magnitudes observed in each device differ, the normalized V_T drift is very consistent, suggesting that the same mechanism (near-interfacial oxide traps) is the dominant cause with only a variation in the number of active traps. Although the older-vintage (2014) Vendor A devices performed similarly to Vendor B's devices, the newer Vendor A (2015) devices showed more drift under PBS. Vendor C's devices shifted so far as to drive the I_D measurements into the noise, hiding data at longer stress times. The Si MOSFET barely moved and shifted by less than 40 mV.

Figure 4. V_T drift during stress (left) and recovery (right) of various SiC DMOSEFETs during 25 °C PBS ($V_{GS} = +15$ V), along with a Si DMOSEFET.

NBS results for 25 °C are shown in Fig. 5; as opposed to PBS, we saw a stronger initial V_T drift followed by weaker dependence on t_S . This seems likely due to enhanced capture/emission from a much larger change in the Fermi level between stress and measurement (C-V techniques have been shown to record larger shifts under NBS than I-V [12]). As opposed to PBS, Vendor A's 2014 and 2015 devices show similar behavior while Vendor B's have a larger response and Vendor C's again shifted out of range. The Si control MOSFET behaved as before, drifting less than 40 mV towards the stress bias.

Figure 5. Identical to Fig. 4, except showing V_T drift following 25 °C NBS ($V_{GS} = -15$ V).

B. High-Temperature (175 °C) Bias Stressing

In Fig. 6, the temperature dependence of V_T drift during PBTS is shown; this data is for a Vendor B device but the shape and temperature dependence are typical for devices from both Vendors A and B. Vendor C's devices were not temperature stressed due to their excessive drifts at 25 °C. As device temperature was raised, the net V_T drift actually improved although the slope during stress remained nearly constant. The

enhanced V_T drift recovery at short t_R is primarily responsible for the temperature differences during stressing and is consistent with the thermal emission of electrons from fast interface traps near the SiC conduction band or possibly tunneling of charge from the fastest SOTs.

Figure 6. V_T drift for Vendor B devices during PBTS stress (left) and recovery (right) as a function of temperature. The shape and temperature dependence are the same for Vendor A devices.

The V_T drift under NBTS, shown in Fig. 7, showed a marked difference between Vendor A and B devices (note the vertical scales). Vendor A's show a decrease in drift at higher temperatures like the PBTS case, as well as a consistently weak dependence on t_S as was seen at 25 °C NBS. Vendor B's, on the other hand, saw an NBTS drift that got worse with temperature along with a rapid onset of additional drift after 10^3 - 10^4 s of stress. Recovery of the drift for Vendor B's was significantly slower, suggesting that more of the damage is permanent in this case.

Figure 7. NBTS response of V_T drift as a function of temperature for a Vendor B device (top) and Vendor A device (bottom).

C. Room-Temperature Gate Switching

AC gate switching can be considered as a more accurate predictor of actual operating reliability than DC stresses alone, although it is not done in standard qualification tests. As shown in Fig. 8, which plots the drift in V_T^+ and V_T^- (starting values for each parameter are indicated in the legends) along with the hysteresis ΔV_T , both Vendor A & B devices had a low level of V_T drift – indicative of deeper SOTs slowly coming towards a quasi-equilibrium charge state with the oscillating gate bias. Notably, ΔV_T does not move, meaning that there is no

significant change in those fast states that can follow the gate signal. The most notable difference between Vendor A & B devices in this data set is in the magnitude of ΔV_T — 0.90 V and 0.10 V respectively.

Figure 8. 25 °C AC stress response of the most recent Vendor A&B parts.

D. High-Temperature (175 °C) Gate Switching

Fig. 9 shows how these devices respond to gate switching at elevated temperatures. Superficially the behavior is similar to the room temperature results; initially Vendor A devices drift negatively and Vendor B devices drift positively. However, the response of the Vendor A device shows a “kink” in V_T^+ at 10^2 s and in V_T^- at 10^4 s causing both parameters to drift positively. The positive drift in V_T is consistent with the generation of new acceptor-like interface traps, while the positive change in ΔV_T indicates activation of switching oxide traps [2]. The Vendor B device only shows a moderate increase in the V_T drift rate.

Additionally, ΔV_T for both vendors has significantly decreased relative to the room temperature values as has been previously reported in DC measurements [13]. The Vendor B device has decreased so much as to reverse direction; V_T^+ following PBTS is now more negative than V_T^- following NBTS. Simple charge trapping alone cannot account for such a reversal, suggesting the presence of either mobile ions or polarized charges in the gate oxide. The Vendor A devices likely share this same mechanism given those devices’ similar negative trend in ΔV_T with temperature.

Although AC stresses are generally considered to be easier on BTI-prone devices [14], there are some results showing an increase in trap generation rates and reduction in TDDB lifetimes [15]. There are few public reports available investigating V_T stability of power MOSFETs after prolonged

switching, though [16] investigated DC characterization of similar devices and saw no more than +0.2 V drift in V_T during a 1,000 hr, 150 °C unipolar (+20 V/0 V, 20 kHz) switching (the interruption of stress and delay before measurement likely resulted in greatly reduced V_T drift based on our results).

Figure 9. 175 °C AC stress response of the most recent Vendor A&B parts.

IV. CONCLUSION

Threshold voltage stability during bias and temperature stressing of three SiC DMOSFET vendors were compared using fast measurement techniques, which consistently show much larger instabilities (~ 2 – $5\times$) than conventional (slow) measurements. Although there was some variation observed in the magnitude of threshold drifts under unipolar stress, all devices show a similar stress and recover behavior. Temperature-dependent unipolar stress showed consistent trends under positive bias stress, but those trends diverged under negative bias stress.

Additionally, V_T measurements during 10 kHz gate switching revealed potentially significant hysteresis. Elevating the device temperature tended to move the magnitude of the hysteresis more negative and suggests there may be mobile-ion drift or polarization charge present. High temperature also showed evidence of new interface- and switching oxide-trap activation with stress time in Vendor A devices from the positive drift in V_T and increasing ΔV_T (whereas Vendor B’s were more stable and did not show significant changes).

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